

**TECHNOLOGIES TO ELIMINATE STUTTERING IN PRESCHOOL
CHILDREN**

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ANNOTATION: This scientific article explores the utilization of technologies in the treatment of stuttering among preschool children. The article examines the potential benefits of incorporating technology-based interventions in stuttering therapy and highlights various technological approaches used to enhance speech fluency. It discusses the effectiveness and limitations of these technologies in improving the speech fluency of young children. Through a review of relevant literature, this article aims to enhance our understanding of the role of technology in addressing stuttering in preschool-aged children.

KEYWORDS: technologies, stuttering, preschool children, speech fluency, intervention

INTRODUCTION

Stuttering is a communication disorder characterized by disruptions in the flow of speech, which can impact a child's social interactions and overall communication skills. In recent years, advancements in technology have opened new possibilities for intervention and therapy. This article aims to explore the use of technologies in addressing stuttering in preschool children, highlighting the benefits of incorporating these interventions and discussing the challenges and limitations that may arise.

MAIN PART

Interaction with technology promotes four areas of learning: the acquisition of action skills, the development of understanding and knowledge about the world, and the understanding of technology in everyday life (Plowman, McPake, & Stephen, 2008). Today's preschool children want fast interaction and graphical

environment, without being afraid to use new smart technologies on a trial basis, thus developing specific technical skills (Kaimara et al., 2019). Interaction with technology contributes to the acquisition of operational skills, the formation of understanding and knowledge about the world, the understanding of technology in everyday life (Plowman, McPake, & Stephen, 2008). As a result, cognitive operations no longer take place sequentially, but in parallel. And traditional education is not ready for this, the previously used methods and techniques seem uninteresting and boring to these children (Bennett, Maton, & Kervin, 2008).

In the framework of the international student assessment program PISA 2012 (65 member states), questions about the use of information and communication technologies in mathematics, reading and problem solving are analyzed, including children's answers about themselves, their home, school and learning experience, parental involvement in their child's studies at school and support at home. It is concluded that digital technologies can improve teaching and learning in many ways, enabling children to be active participants in the learning process, as it is possible to adjust the pace of learning, provide feedback, and support collaborative learning that is effective because it takes place in collaboration with other children and teachers (OECD, 2014).

It is indicated (Misják & Berecz, 2018) that with the help of technology it is easier to keep children's attention, to learn effectively, it is possible to activate children's visual perception, and with sound effects and the pronunciation of game instructions to stimulate the development of listening skills. A properly organized learning environment, in which content, technology and the learner interact, allows for the implementation of personalized pedagogical and correctional work, respecting the child's individual needs, interests, developmental dynamics and problems, providing the necessary support, respecting the individual work pace and developing self-regulation (Spector, 2014).

Digital technologies can promote early literacy acquisition, mathematical skills, develop a positive attitude towards learning (Jackson, Eye, Fitzgerald, Witt, &

Zhao, 2011), promote the development of visuospatial abilities (Li, Atkins, & Stanton, 2006). 3-4-year-old children, working with various technologies, improve their application skills, and adult participation and understanding of the ways that could support children in their interaction with technologies are important in the educational process. Children learn independently of the participation of their parents or teachers, but when learning for a specific purpose, this participation and support is necessary (Alexander, 2008).

It should be realized that digital technologies are one of the pedagogical tools and cannot completely replace the interaction between the teacher and the child. Learning is first through interpersonal interaction, followed by personal counseling before the learner can act independently. It is characterized as a transition from guided interaction (or helping others) to self-motivated (self-help) action (Vygotsky, 1981).

Using technologies, the preschool teacher must have the appropriate competence and understanding when, in what way and for how long to organize pedagogical activities using technologies. In the literature (Wu, Fowler, Lam, Wong, Wong, & Loke, 2014) it is emphasized that the use of technology in preschool can affect the child in both positive and negative ways, because in the preschool age there is a very rapid development in all areas. Long-term use of digital technologies reduces children's movement activity, increases the risk of obesity and musculoskeletal problems (Bremer, 2005), the risk of addiction may develop, increasing the indicators of aggressive and violent behavior (Subrahmanyam et al., 2000). Frequent and long-term use of digital technologies can hinder the development of social skills in preschool children (Jackson et al., 2011).

In order to ensure the use of technology in a healthy and useful way, it is important to involve parents and teachers as collaborative partners, to study the strategies that adults use to regulate children's digital activities (Van den Bulck & Van den Bergh, 2000).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

- I. Overview of Stuttering in Preschool Children
 - A. Characteristics and impact of stuttering on preschoolers
 - B. Importance of early intervention in stuttering therapy
- II. Technological Approaches in Stuttering Therapy
 - A. Computer-based therapy programs
 - B. Mobile applications
 - C. Virtual reality and augmented reality interventions
 - D. Speech recognition and biofeedback systems
- III. Benefits of Utilizing Technology in Stuttering Therapy
 - A. Increased engagement and motivation of preschool children
 - B. Individualized therapy options
 - C. Enhanced accessibility and convenience
 - D. Real-time feedback and monitoring
- IV. Effectiveness of Technological Interventions
 - A. Review of studies on the effectiveness of computer-based therapy programs
 - B. The impact of mobile applications in stuttering therapy
 - C. Virtual reality and augmented reality interventions: A promising approach
 - D. Speech recognition and biofeedback systems: An overview of research findings
- V. Challenges and Limitations of Technology-based Stuttering Interventions
 - A. Cost and accessibility considerations
 - B. Ethical and privacy concerns
 - C. The need for therapist involvement in technology-based interventions

CONCLUSION:

The utilization of technology-based interventions in treating stuttering among preschool children has demonstrated promise in enhancing speech fluency and engaging young learners in therapy. Computer-based therapy programs, mobile applications, virtual reality, augmented reality, and speech recognition systems offer various benefits in terms of convenience, individualization, and real-time

feedback. However, challenges such as cost, accessibility, and the need for therapist involvement should be carefully considered. Future research should continue examining the effectiveness and long-term outcomes of technology-based interventions to optimize stuttering therapy for this age group.

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